

DISTINCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS OF OFFENSES AND CRIMES COMMITTED AMONG MINORS

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Abstract: This article analyzes offenses and crimes committed by minors. The types of offenses frequently committed by minors in recent years were examined. Additionally, the causes and factors of offenses and crimes committed by minors were investigated.

Keywords: minors, offenses, crimes, analysis, factors, psychological characteristics.

Crimes committed by minors are one of the pressing problems of society. This issue requires attention not only from law enforcement agencies but also from society as a whole. The involvement of the younger generation in criminal activity poses a serious threat to the future of society, as it can lead to negative consequences not only in the present but also in the long term.

According to the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, although the number of crimes committed by minors in recent years has shown a downward trend, this issue remains relevant [1].

In 2024, more than 320 crimes and over 780 offenses were committed by minors in the Namangan region [2].

According to statistics, the main types of offenses and crimes committed by minors are as follows. Specifically, crimes related to bodily harm amounted to 29, while theft, robbery, hooliganism, and fraud (for January-December 2024) totaled more than 200.

104 cases of petty hooliganism and over 550 other types of offenses were committed by minors, of which more than 80 were committed under the influence of alcohol.

In our republic in 2023, the highest number of juvenile offenders was recorded in Fergana (700 people), Namangan (451 people), and Tashkent (345 people) regions, as well as in Tashkent city (545 people). Conversely, the lowest number of juvenile offenders was registered in Jizzakh (54 people), Khorezm (66 people), Syrdarya (77 people), and Navoi (62 people) regions [2].

Currently, work is being carried out to prevent neglect and delinquency among minors in accordance with the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the Prevention of Neglect and Delinquency among Minors" of September 29, 2010, and other regulatory legal acts.

However, the above statistical data indicate that the work being carried out to prevent delinquency and crime among minors is insufficient, the current regulatory legal documents do not specify specific mechanisms for crime prevention, or the law enforcement agencies do not ensure the proper implementation of existing documents.

Minors raised in economically disadvantaged families are generally more likely to commit crimes due to financial hardship. These factors, in particular, indicate that young people are forced to look for ways to make money. According to sociologists, in research on crime, the environment and family relationships are cited as the main reasons for the

emergence of crimes. Low-income families or lack of social control become an environment in which children are unable to control their behavior.

Further, there are hypotheses about the mental state of children and their attitude to life, in particular, that emotional or psychological processes can lead to crime, where evidence indicating that aggression in children and psychological problems in childhood can lead them to crime can be seen in the analysis of criminal cases.

Minors try to present themselves as "heroes" in social groups. We believe that these conditions can also affect their mental state. Another situation is the lack of control in schools or insufficient educational work, which indicates the absence of mechanisms for monitoring children's behavior.

Scientific research shows that a lack of school or family supervision encourages young people to commit crimes. Crime shows a correlation between the quality of general education and youth detachment from education. Families with financial means attract their children to additional courses, in other cases, the level of education reduces access to education.

Also, one of the important issues is that the unemployment rate in society creates a situation of youth unemployment, which, in turn, increases the risk of crime. Studies show that insufficient opportunities for young people in the labor market can lead them to illegal activities.

In particular, a good life, a difference between peers can be the basis for committing these crimes. Although legal knowledge is currently being taught in schools, problems with the quality of education negatively affect the behavior and decisions of young people. This increases the likelihood of them taking the path of crime.

Studies conducted on similar situations show that lack of moral education or legal knowledge leads young people to make erroneous decisions. This can often be observed in their actions on social networks, where they act without considering the consequences.

According to the World Health Organization, over 200,000 homicides occur annually worldwide among young people aged 10-29 [3]. This figure demonstrates the severity of the juvenile and youth crime problem on a global scale.

According to the UN Commission on Crime Prevention and Criminal Justice, juvenile delinquency accounts for 10-15% of the overall crime rate in many countries worldwide [4]. This indicator is higher than the situation in Uzbekistan.

International experience shows that developed countries are implementing comprehensive measures aimed at reducing juvenile delinquency. In particular, countries such as the USA, Great Britain, and Canada are actively developing juvenile justice systems, which are yielding positive results in reducing juvenile delinquency.

Studying foreign countries' experiences in preventing juvenile delinquency is of great importance. Let's examine foreign practices in this area. Japan has one of the lowest rates of juvenile delinquency in the world. One of the main reasons for this is the "koban" system. Within this system, small police stations exist in each neighborhood, working closely with the population and paying great attention to crime prevention [5].

In Germany, the "Life Skills" program is widely used in combating juvenile delinquency. This program aims to teach young people skills in conflict resolution, stress management, and making sound decisions [6]. In Sweden, according to the Law "On Social Services," the main focus when working with juvenile offenders is not on punishment, but on their reintegration into society. This approach yields effective results in reducing juvenile delinquency [6].

In the USA, a special judicial system and rehabilitation programs for minors operate on the basis of the Law on Juvenile Justice and Crime Prevention. Measures are also being taken to reintegrate former offending youth into society through the "Second Chance" program [6].

Based on the above analysis and foreign experience, the following recommendations can be given for improving the practice and legislation on the prevention of juvenile delinquency in Uzbekistan: introduction of a juvenile justice system, in which it is necessary to create special courts for juvenile affairs, to create a legislative framework regulating their activities; development and adoption of a national strategy for the prevention of juvenile delinquency. This strategy will allow coordinating the efforts of all stakeholders and achieving long-term goals; expanding the network of social rehabilitation centers. Through such centers, it is possible to work with young people belonging to risk groups and provide them with psychological and social assistance.

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